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Meaningful Learning in English as a Foreign Language Classrooms: A culinary experience as Comprehensible Input

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Abstract

Foreign Language educators and researchers still refine meaningful instruction and engagement to motivate secondary education students. This research aims to enhance learning environments and analyze students' exposure to English vocabulary through a collection of culinary videos as Comprehensible Input in English as foreign language (EFL) classrooms. The participants were high school students from a public educational institution in Manta-Ecuador. This study is ascribed to the post-modern paradigm, using a hybrid approach and audio-visual technology research as a teaching resource. The instrument used is the students' motivation for learning of Acevedo, et al. (2022). The techniques for determining this research were non-random sampling and data collection with surveys, interviews, and class observations. The research results demonstrated that learners recognize foreign language vocabulary when creating a cooking recipe or when the teaching process is authentic, dynamic, and innovative. Moreover, exposing learners to an artistic experience increases participants' motivation to practice a foreign language. It is concluded that EFL learning environments can be more meaningful when instructors use videos as Comprehensible Input.

Keywords: Comprehensible Input, Multimedia, Cooking, Meaningful Learning, English as a Foreign Language

1. Introduction

Mastering a high level of English represents an added value within any professional profile (Yang, 2011). In this sense, one of the most significant challenges facing modern education is to maintain students' interest in learning. Hence, institutions such as Canadian College (2021) allow technological advances, combined with high doses of meaningful learning, to fortify their teaching processes, adjusting dynamic, entertaining, and effective learning. This success is due to computer tools and mobile equipment in conjunction with approaches and theories such as Comprehensible Input, Computer Assisted Language Learning, and Gamification.

This article presents the literature and theoretical review on Comprehensible Input in second language acquisition, learner motivation for foreign language learning, and the contribution of multimedia technology in Modern Education. Thus, the Comprehensible Input theory developed by linguist Stephen Krashen, is remarkably effective

in helping learners develop their English communicative skills permitting learners to acquire language intrinsically and non-consciously (Bilash, 2011). Similarly, Tina Hargaden states that Comprehensible Input is an essential ingredient, like the food in a meal. She expresses that Comprehensible Input is not a method but is the secret ingredient that allows educators to interact within every language classroom (cited in Gunning, 2021). Therefore, this research attempts to identify how Comprehensible Input theory enhances English acquisition through meaningful events such as cooking activities.

On the other hand, Motivation is an essential factor in Language Learning. According to Fernández (2002), it is the basis of second language learning because it allows educators to have an adequate context for teaching. There are four fundamental elements: extrinsic or instrumental Motivation, integrative or intrinsic Motivation, goals and expectations, and context (Alfaro & Alvarado, 2016).

In addition, learning a second language and using technological resources facilitates comprehension, autonomy, teamwork, flexibility, and critical thinking of learners. As a result, Researchers' Motivation is to create more meaningful learning environments involving the use of technology in Ecuadorian high school students, highlighting students' English language comprehension, reading, and listening skills.

This research contributes to Goal 4 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (2021), promoting inclusive and equitable quality education for lifelong learning opportunities. Research questions answered in this paper are:

1. How can be used videos as Comprehensible Input in EFL classrooms?
2. What is the contribution of videos as comprehensive input at EFL classes?
3. Are students motivated when using videos to learn a foreign language?
4. Does using audio-visual technological resources improve the current EFL instruction?

In essence, this article aims to create more realistic and dynamic learning environments in EFL classes for high school learners through technology and culinary experiences as Comprehensible Input.

2. Literature review

2.1. Comprehensible Input in Second Language Acquisition

Although Comprehensible Input (CI) has become a buzzword in language education, educators would be mistaken to disregard CI as yet another education fad. Comprehensible Input theory is solidly constructed upon decades of hypotheses and their respective research. It is the basis of the current Second Language Acquisition (SLA) theory (Ash, 2017).

According to Tajudeen and Zakaria (2021) and Schütz (2019), Krashen proposed five theories to explain language acquisition; these theories are collectively referred to as the monitor model in Applied Linguistics Literature, they are: The Acquisition-Learning Distinction, Natural Order Hypothesis, The Natural Order Hypothesis, and The Input Hypothesis (Krashen et al., 2018). Krashen applied his theories to respond to Second Language Acquisition (SLA) questions. He argued that his hypotheses shed light on almost all the issues currently debated in second language practice. However, among these theories, the theory of Comprehensible Input is prominent in current Language Teaching (Lichtman & VanPatten, 2021).

This work is related to the process of language acquisition thus, the Comprehensible Input theory is related to students' second language acquisition process. In addition, Comprehensible Input supports learners to achieve a linguistic adduct (Input) containing language structures slightly more complex above the common proficiency level. This Input is comprehensible due to context, situation, extralinguistic factors, and knowledge. This hypothesis refers exclusively to the processes and outcomes of Acquisition (Centro Virtual Cervantes, 2022). Additionally, DiSabatino (2019) refutes the most crucial feature of Comprehensible Input: the flow must be understandable. There will be no acquisition if the pupil cannot understand the message. Regardless, Classroom

Teaching will be effective if the CI becomes "noise" and distracts scholars. The educator can adapt the Input to learners' level by following the "I + 1" rule, i.e., giving them slightly above their comprehension level.

Furthermore, Ash (2017) states that Compressible Input can condense into three fundamental pillars of CI: comprehensible, compelling, and attentive teaching, which have been repeatedly corroborated by research. Mason (2016) states, "there has never been a language acquisition approach has been validated to this extent, not only for its effectiveness but also for its efficiency." As language educators, incorporating Comprehensible Input into language teaching constructs programs based on research and scholarship.

On the other hand, Patrick's (2019) study argues that the United States has seen an inquisitive and probably unpredictable movement in how nearly extinct languages are taught. Comprehensible Input has become a vehicle for change affecting classrooms, teacher training programs, and standing worldwide language organizations.

On the other hand, Tajudeen and Zakaria (2021) explain that Krashen's theory of Comprehensible Input has been criticized for three main reasons: vagueness in his theory, loss of definitions of the constructs contained in the vision, and lack of consistency. However, Liu (2015) summarizes the CI's journey in three stages; first, he traced the boundary between comprehension and acquisition. Then, CI was criticized for the absence of empirical evidence and inability. Eventually, its overemphasis on comprehensibility was necessary for language acquisition. Finally, some linguists and pedagogues, such as Brown, Palmer, Gregg, and McLaughlin, have attempted to apply the i+1 input model to teaching different foreign languages such as German and Thai. Regardless, classroom applications have faced setbacks, blaming Krashen for vaguely postulating a model without considering its pedagogical applications (Payne, 2011).

However, a recent Krashen and Mason (2020) research argues that comprehensibility is insufficient, but other factors make up "optimal input." Krashen et al. (2018) present four crucial characteristics of Optimal Input: (1) It is comprehensible, which means total transparency, (2) Language Acquisition does not require understanding every word and every part of every word. It is exciting: it is "compelling," so interesting that you temporarily forget to listen or read in another language, (3) Optimal input is rich in language that contributes to the message and flow of the story or text, and (3) Language acquisition is a gradual process: each time we encounter a new element in an understandable context, we acquire a small amount of meaning and form (Krashen & Mason, 2020). In essence, the optimal input hypothesis assumes input, not output, and results in subconscious language acquisition.

2.2. Students' motivation for learning a foreign language

Motivation plays an essential role in learning English as a foreign language (EFL). Motivation is considered the key to English language learning and one of the most critical factors affecting language learners' success, defining it as one of the crucial factors limiting English language learning. According to Sinap et al. (2021) and Tashlanovna et al. (2020), results demonstrate that the more motivated learners are, the more successful they will be in language learning. In this context, Aalayina and Yulfi (2021) state that motivation encourages learners to achieve their learning goals. Therefore, scholars will be enthusiastic in the Teaching-Learning process to study English effectively. In addition, Uddiniyah and Silfia (2019), Aalayina and Yulfi (2021), and Nuraeni and Aisyah (2020) confirm that motivation is the process that gives encouragement, direction, and persistence to behavior; hence, motivation is energetic, focused, and enduring behavior. Moreover, they argue that certain behaviors must support success to achieve desired goals. They assert that motivation is a decision people make based on the experiences, effort, or dreams they propose to accomplish. Almost all work undertaken requires motivation as an activator and stimulus to complete the best action.

Nowell et al. (2017) and Subakthiasih and Putri (2020) present two types of motivation in Learning English: Integrative and Instrumental motivation. Integrative motivation denotes learning a language to communicate with people from another culture. In contrast, instrumental learning a language to fulfil specific positive goals, such as getting a job or taking an exam (cited in Aalayina & Yulfi, 2021, p. 442).

Uddiniyah and Silfia (2019) analyzed how intrinsic motivation tends to be higher than extrinsic motivation in English language learning. A Peña's (2019) study conducted at Escuela de Lenguas de la Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador reveals that most scholars are intrinsically motivated due to their desire to study the language independently. The students comprehend the importance of learning a universal language such as English, which is present in the primary forms of communication, such as the Internet and books. However, Nuraeni and Aisyah (2020) indicate that most learners have extrinsic motivation, and only a few have intrinsic motivation. Purnama et al. (2019) conclude that English learners have high motivation to learn English; regardless of their reason, instructors must be more creative in using media, strategies, or material delivered in teaching activities to enhance students' motivation. "If there is no motivation, the teaching-learning process objectives will not be achieved."

Scholars' interest in learning English is because English allows them to communicate easily with people worldwide; presently, students use English via social networks, such as Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp, to contact others. In addition, English provides learners with information about world news and facts concerning native speakers' culture and permits learners to obtain a job (Aalayina & Yulfi, 2021).

2.3. Multimedia and educational Technology

The idea of teaching a language through videos is currently in vogue. They provide a solid context through which language teaching is about meaning and practice; giving "reality." Videos create a more engaging sensory experience than print materials alone. They provide a resource that can be viewed anywhere with an Internet connection, including laptops, tablets, and smartphones. Simultaneously, videos increase knowledge retention, as they can be paused and replayed as many times as needed. Therefore, they greatly aid learning incredibly complex and highly visual subjects, such as step-by-step procedures, problem-solving, or language learning. Finally, they increase digital literacy and communication mastery, which are essential 21st-century skills (Bevan, 2020).

According to González et al. (2017), educators use videos as a facilitator of autonomous learning, a tool to develop digital knowledge, and teaching-learning process. For instance, different educational videos made by instructors are currently circulating on platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, and even TikTok adapted to the subject's programming as videos of cultural and artistic dissemination. In addition, they aim to present cultural, creative, and scientific-technical forms to dispersed audiences, where contents associated with the advancement of science and technology are exposed (Posligua & Zambrano, 2020).

Thus, García (2015) declares that learners appreciate information better when accessing audio-visual content because they better identify the class content. Similarly, Rodríguez and Fernández (2017) state that online resources represent one of the most common learning tools among scholars since recent information is digitised. In line with Velasco et al. (2018), educational videos constitute a powerful instrument to support learning. For instance, YouTube has shown a growing influence in EFL classrooms, resulting in a higher rate of educators with skills related to the proliferation of technological implements (Sharma & Sharma, 2021).

In this sense, Gutiérrez et al. (2019) consider that audio-visual content in the educational process must have integrity and accuracy to avoid confusing students. Therefore, Senís (2019) assures that YouTube conducts this process to achieve its role. Furthermore, this platform is prominent because of the wide range of content hosted in this space and the possibilities it offers due to its attractive and easy-to-understand characteristics (López, 2018). Similarly, those who use this social medium are notable because it constitutes an essential phenomenon for disseminating knowledge in the educational field.

As Romero et al. (2017) claimed, videos came into use decades ago. Therefore, it is not the first-time video in Education studied phenomenon. However, its impact transcended after the emergence of the Internet and pandemic. Increasingly, society and scholars turn to YouTube or video platforms to learn everything from how a car works to acquiring a language just by watching videos they like. "Undoubtedly, when a person turns to this type of media, he or she uses processes based on the theories of free/creative or discovery learning" (p. 517).

In line with Pérez and Cuecuecha's (2019) and Kaltura's (2019) "The State of Video in Education" report, they showed that using videos and entertainment platforms as didactic material improves students' performance by becoming more interested in audio-visual content than traditional teaching processes.

Concerning Hudson (2020) and López and Gómez (2015), the digital platform goes hand in hand with incorporating ICT in the classroom because it has become a direct outlet to in-person and online Education, as it is a free resource that provides flexibility for autonomous learning. Martinez (2016) and Kosterelioglu (2016) argue that new technologies and the Internet have not only changed the way we communicate and relate to each other. It has also changed the way children, youth, and adults learn. Therefore, today's educators must be aware of and apply new methodologies to break the existing gap between students and the traditional textbook-based teaching method (Posligua & Zambrano, 2020).

On the other hand, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has proved to be a global health crisis that has threatened millions of people worldwide. This threat led to the total closure of schools, colleges, and later universities, which would have to adapt to distance education online, leaving aside in-person classes (Unger & Meiran, 2020). In Ecuador, the Ministry of Education (MinEdu) promoted a COVID-19 Educational Plan to provide pedagogical and methodological tools that encourage and strengthen an adaptable educational model (Ministerio de Educación, 2020).

Recent studies have demonstrated that the current generation of learners routinely uses these tools for educational purposes (Lone et al., 2018). Therefore, virtual Education was promoted by innovative learning tools and multimedia resources such as computer-assisted learning (CALL) and mobile applications (Vagg et al., 2020). Consequently, multimedia is effective for learning: animations effectively stimulate learner interest and thus enhance the learning experience and augmented reality improves learners' cognitive skills by providing a platform that combines digital and physical parameters (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017). Thus, the appropriate use of multimedia in teaching transforms the learning environment from teacher-centred to learner-centred, transforming all aspects of human life (Guan et al., 2018).

For instance, Mofareh's investigation (2019) expressed dissatisfaction with the traditional language learning method in classroom environments, based on teacher-centred approaches without attending to learners' needs. As a result, Mofareh's investigation indirectly pointed out the importance of technology in language learning, focused on computer-assisted language learning (CALL).

Multimedia resources have modified perceptions about curricular innovation, mainly in recent decades. Studies, such as Meza (2015) and Senís (2019), argue that via media, teaching-learning processes have improved since students, regardless of their level, have a better disposition towards their academic training when audio-visual resources are incorporated in the classroom.

Multimedia-assisted English teaching has become an inevitable trend in Education, enabling new skills and new fun environments to enhance multimedia resources such as images and videos. It bases its etymology on specific learning theories such as constructivism, cognitive psychology, humanistic psychology (Guan et al., 2018). Then, (1) Constructivist learning theory assumes that the learning environment should be a location to learn together using various tools and information resources to solve problems, (2) Cognitive psychology emphasizes learners' internal psychological processes. Studying English is a lengthy process, so teachers must direct study activities. CALL can create good conditions and a learning environment for learners, and (3) Humanistic psychology explores language teaching from psychology. It emphasizes the dignity and value of the human being. These theories enable educators to have a good understanding of multimedia resources. In summary, CALL can help teachers find new teaching methods providing learners with good choices of time and content (Incedayi, 2018).

According to Marpa (2021), multimedia is considered the most interactive and powerful individual learning technology platform. It has penetrated education systems and created new approaches to school systems and learning processes. Guan et al. (2018) express that multimedia is widely used in English teaching with the development of science and technology. Besides, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) can inspire

students' enthusiasm for learning English and optimize the EFL classrooms environment. With the combination of CALL, EFL classrooms have ceased to be monotonous. It has become one of the highlights of English Language Teaching by enhancing its English learning process, distinctive teaching characteristics, and teaching environment.

3. Methodology

This research is subscribed to the post-modern paradigm, using a hybrid approach and audio-visual technology research as a teaching medium. This investigation used randomized experimental techniques, quasi-experimental techniques, survey techniques, interview techniques, observation techniques, and tests.

The experimental design of the research corresponds to the pre-test and post-test (Rodríguez & Fernández, 2017), giving one before and one after the observation of the videos. For the data analysis, three categories were established: the teaching-learning process of a second language, the vocabulary of cooking in English, and the use of the educational video.

3.1. The sample

The selected population was learners from a public school in Manta-Ecuador. The Project invited 42 students of the first BGU, but 14 accepted the research invitation. The average age was 15.2 years, 48% were boys, and 52% were girls. Six were taken as experimental groups, and the others were assigned as control groups.

This sample falls within the typology of non-random sampling, as a whole group of participants is taken, without it being voluntary or randomly selected.

3.2. The instruments

The instruments applied to carry out the research were:

Educational intervention. Educational intervention. It consists of three stages: (1) Creations of a dessert e-book to get a general idea of dessert preferences, (2) Demonstration class-diagnosis to introducing students to learning a language through culinary arts activities; and finally, (3) Videos as Comprehensible Input, which consists in the elaboration of six culinarian videos in which participants use EFL.

Interview guide. This instrument consists of five questions to determine interest in cooking videos and recipes. The research team developed the survey using the Google Form platform. In addition, the pilot video was attached to acquire feedback from pupils, get a general sample of their preferences, and modify or add to the e-book. A panel of specialists evaluated the instrument and recommended concentrating on the questions related to recipes in foreign language learning and reducing the number of questions. Once the corrections were made, the instrument was launched.

Attitude and motivation survey. This instrument was adjusted from the investigation of Acevedo, et al. (2022). It consists of 7 questions related to the attitudes and motivation of learners when learning a second language through culinary activities. The instrument was adjusted to the socio-cultural conditions and age of the participants. The instrument was evaluated by an expert panel that recommended improvements in the language used to ensure participants' understanding of the questions. The research team developed the survey form using the Google Form platform.

Observation form. This instrument aspired to determine how participants could learn English vocabulary using audio-visual material. The observation was executed during the undergraduate teachers' practice processes for three months in 2019. The instrument consists of 10 items indicating positive and negative expressions of the participants concerning learning a foreign language, reading practice, writing using English vocabulary related to preparing desserts.

3.3. Process

This research consists of the following nine stages:

Stage 1: Organization and selection of participants. The selection process of potential participants was organized, taking as a reference a public school in which 14 pupils participated.

Stage 2: Identification of participants' preferences. A survey was conducted to determine the dessert preferences of the participants. The survey was designed with the research group on the Google form platform.

Stage 3: Selection of recipes and development of the e-book. Stage 2 served as a reference for selecting the recipes and the design of the e-book. The e-book consisted of six recipes divided into three categories. For this purpose, materials were validated by a group of researchers.

Stage 4: Production of the pilot video. Once the selection had been made and the preferences identified, the first pilot video of 1 minute and 52 minutes was uploaded on the YouTube platform.

Stage 5: Validation of the pilot video. The validation consisted of two stages, validation by the research group and participants. It was noted that videos needed more production and a longer running time.

Stage 6: Elaboration of the collection of videos, recipes, and tests. Six videos of at least 10 minutes were produced and uploaded to the YouTube platform. In the same way, a multiple-choice test was designed on the Quiz platform to determine the comprehension of the vocabulary learnt in each video.

Stage 7: Elaboration of the research instruments. A survey related to the attitudes and motivation of learners when learning a second language through culinary activities was designed. On the other hand, an observation sheet was designed to determine how participants could learn English vocabulary used in cooking through videos. All instruments were designed and validated by the research group.

Stage 8: Analysis of the information obtained. During the collection of data and information obtained, it was found that 90% of the students understood the English vocabulary of the recipes, and 10% had difficulties. The video collection serves as a tool for future ESL teachers to introduce English through innovative, flexible, and dynamic videos.

Stage 9: Writing the document. Finally, an academic document was written where all the data obtained from the research is evidenced.

4. Results

The presentation of the results follows the order of the research questions presented in the introduction section.

4.1. Educational intervention

In answer to the question 1: How can be used videos as Comprehensive Input in EFL classrooms?

Creation of a dessert e-book. A template from Nestlé (2019) website was taken as a reference, following the basic patterns for creating an e-book. This e-book is divided into three sections, the first two "common desserts," the second two healthy desserts and finally, two desserts of my authorship. Moreover, a survey was conducted to determine students' dessert preferences and, depending on the results, to modify or add recipes.}

Demonstrative cooking class - diagnosis. - A demonstration class was created via the YouTube platform with the topic "How to Make a Peanut Butter and Jelly Sandwich" to introduce pupils to learning a language through culinary arts activities is possible.

Videos production as comprehensive input. - A collection of six videos were created, following the first demo class format, the videos are divided as follows: Apple pie, iced coffee, Chocolate Mug Cake, Butter Cookies, Red Velvet Cookies, and Chocolate Chips Cookies, then taking a test carried out on the Quizizz platform to evaluate the vocabulary learned in the videos. Finally, the videos will be uploaded to the YouTube platform to reach the community of scholars who desire to learn English and prepare desserts.

Table 1: Lesson plan using video as comprehensive input.

Script and Lesson Plan # 1	
Level: A2	
TOPIC: APPLE PIE	

Time 6 min	Audio/ Text/ Content	Short Lesson plan
	<p>Introduction Hey, guys. Welcome back to another video with “COME LEARN ENGLISH AND COOK WITH ANDRES.” Today we are going to prepare an APPLE PIE. Yes, as you heard, an apple pie, for lovers to apples, easy to prepare and easy to get the ingredients. So don't lose our time, and. Let's begin!</p> <p>Body For this recipe, we are going to use ingredients that most of you guys have at home. But... ANDRES! ... what are the ingredients?!</p> <p>Ingredients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 310gr 2 ½ cups of all-purpose flour - 1 tbs sugar - 1 tsp Salt - 200gr butter - 7tbs cold water) - 4 apples - ½ lemon - 1½tsp cinnamon - 1 tbs brown sugar) - 100gr butter - 3 tbs flour - 50ml milk - ½ cup sugar - ½ cup brown sugar - 6 tbs of iced water <p>APPLE PIE'S DOUGH</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First, add the flour, 1 tbs sugar, 1tsp salt, and the butter in cubs (no with the hands. Use a fork or a spoon) but do not worry if there's still dry mix left. 2. Second, add 6 tbs and mix all until you have a compact mass. 3. Third, put your apple pie's dough in a plastic paper or film, and 4. Finally, put it in the fridge for about an hour <p>APPLE PIE'S PASTE</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First, peel your apples, cut them into squares or whatever shapes you like, and put them into a bowl with ½ cup sugar, 1½tsp cinnamon, and ½ tsp corn-starch. 2. Put 100gr butter, 3tbs flour, and ¼ milk in a pan, mix until they thickened, and add 1 cup sugar. 3. Finally, add the apples and mix again, and let it cool. 	<p>Objective SWBAT: Prepare an APPLE PIE by the video and then practicing vocabulary on Quiz Platform.</p> <p>When/How in the lesson will I check students' progress toward the above Learning Objective? What behaviors/activities will show me whether they have mastered the material?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When the learners do the quiz on the platform. - Ss learn how to prepare an APPLE PIE. <p>Preliminary considerations:</p> <p>a. What vocabulary/grammar/information/skills do your students already know in relation to today's lesson? This is a new recipe with a familiar vocabulary, so most of them probably know some vocabularies.</p> <p>b. What aspects of the lesson do you anticipate your students might find challenging/difficult?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electronic devices - Pronunciation - Internet connection <p>Resources/ Materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-book about the recipes - Laptop - Camera. <p>Quiz</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. After an hour, we separate our dough for the bottom and the cover; we expand the dough for the bottom, put it in our mold add the apples and cover it with the dough that we leave for the cover, previously expanded. We beat an egg, and with a brush, we paint all over the Apple pie and sprinkle sugar. 5. We previously heat the oven to 180°. 6. After that, we put our apple pie in the oven and cook for about 45min. 7. Finally, when the top is golden, we take it out, cool it, and decorate it to our liking. 	
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In answer to question 2: What is the contribution of videos as comprehensive input at EFL classes?

4.2. Videos contribution as a Comprehensive Input

The data collected by the survey is presented following.

Graphic 1: Learners' perception about EFL learning when use videos as Comprehensive Input.

The graph shows that 85.7% of the students surveyed learned new vocabulary in English and have made a peanut butter and jelly sandwich. Similarly, 14.3% of the students did not understand or already know how to make a sandwich. On the other hand, ten students are curious about learning English through cooking activities, three perhaps, and only one pupil does not want to participate. A total of 13 students are dessert lovers, and one not so much. However, 10 participants eat desserts on special occasions and others on weekends.

Further, five students have not tried healthy desserts, three have tried them, and five may have. Finally, Chocolate Volcano and Mini Brownies are the favorite desserts of most of the participants. Nevertheless, only one student prefers the mini lemon tarts. Finally, many students prefer the oatmeal peanut cookies and the strawberry cheesecake, and only one prefers the red fruit smoothie.

In answer to the question 3: Are students motivated when they use videos to learn a foreign language?

4.3. Attitude and Motivation for learning English as a Foreign Language

Graphic 2 shows that 85% of the participants have a positive attitude towards learning English with interactive videos, and 15% do not have a positive attitude. Furthermore, 90% of the learners feel motivated when learning with videos. Almost most scholars have no interest in learning grammar, and about 80% of the participants have

a positive attitude when learning with art activities, and 90% of the learners prefer interactive activities instead of books.

Finally, 70% of the students are interested in making desserts, and 30% are not. Almost all pupils surveyed are motivated to learn English, and the most common reasons are studying, working, and travelling abroad.

Graphic 2: Students' motivation and attitudes for learning EFL

4.3.1. Class observation

The instrument administered was a published form. Observations focused on students' reactions when confronted with new learning techniques, strategies, and culinary activities. In this case, the following statements were taken as a reference: (1) Participants show a positive attitude when confronted with the instructor's new activity. For instance, learners pay more attention when the educator performs a cooking activity than in traditional classes, (2) when the teacher presents activities related to art, the students are attentive, and (3) participants have a specific attachment to innovative activities because they are attentive to tasks in which their skills and interests are the basis for learning. Students do not pay much attention to repetitive activities.

In answer to the question 4: Does using audio-visual technological resources improve the current EFL instruction?

4.4. Students' improvement in EFL vocabulary acquisition

Table 2: Students score and accuracy – practice: Apple pie

Students	Score	Accuracy
Participant 1	3810	100%
Participant 2	3680	100%
Participant 2	3570	100%
Participant 4	3420	100%
Participant 5	2790	75%
Participant 6	2520	75%

Source: class observation (2019)

Table 2 shows the data obtained from the test taken after the participants watched the video. The data were collected by scores represented by response rate and percentages illustrated by accuracy. Four obtained 100%, and two students obtained 75%, i.e., 85% of participants comprehended new words. Furthermore, the apple pie video resonated with the students and the entire YouTube community and currently has over 100 views. Even pronunciation was improved, and a more structured script was used. However, the research group mentioned that the video's quality, production, pronunciation, and content should be improved.

Table 3: Students score and accuracy – practice: Chocolate Mug Cake

Students	Score	Accuracy
Participant 1	5900	100%
Participant 2	5600	100%
Participant 3	5530	100%
Participant 4	4750	83%
Participant 5	4440	83%
Participant	4300	83%

Source: class observation (2019)

Table 4 shows the participants' EFL improvement on vocabulary acquisition.

Table 4: Students' cooking vocabulary acquisition improvement

Student	Pre-test	Post-test	Improvement
1	19	30	11
2	17	25	8
3	13	21	8
4	11	17	6
5	9	13	4
6	7	11	4

Resource: Intervention plan evaluation (2020).

Table 4 indicates the data obtained in the test conducted after the participants watched the video. The data were collected using scores represented by response speed and percentages represented by accuracy. Six questions related to chocolate cake vocabulary were presented. Half of the participants scored 100% on this test, and the other half scored 83%. Although the results are not adequate, the scores are above 4000 and 5000, which means that the level of response speed compensates for the percentage obtained. The video was a success. The students learned the English vocabulary and prepared the Chocolate Mug Cake.

5. Discussion

This study collected recipe videos to corroborate whether the constant use of audio-visual resources generates effective learning. The aim was to investigate whether this educational intervention resulted in a significant acquisition of English language skills and test whether audio-visual technology was an effective teaching method. The results obtained in this research ratify the position of Krashen et al. (2018) concerning the language acquisition theory. Learners' constant exposition to vocabulary in the surrounding context helps them remember a higher number of new words. Similarly, the perspective of Purnama et al. (2019), Tashlanovna et al. (2020), and Sinap et al. (2021) regarding motivation reveal that the more motivated learners are, the more successful they will be in language learning. Therefore, the Educator's community is encouraged to use innovative and didactic resources to keep learners always motivated.

Comparing the research results with Vagg et al. (2020) and Marpa (2021), multimedia is the most interactive and powerful technological tool for scholar learning. Since they provide a solid context through which language teaching is about meaning and practice, giving "reality." Therefore, implementing Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in EFL classrooms could stimulate students' learning interests and optimize the EFL classroom environment.

The surveys' results show that 85% of the learners have a positive attitude towards learning English through interactive videos. 90% of the students feel motivated when understanding via the Internet, i.e., almost most students are not interested in traditionally learning English. On the other hand, 85% of the students have a positive attitude when they learn with artistic and interactive activities instead of books. The data reveals scholars are motivated to learn English; the most common reasons are studying, working, and traveling abroad.

Quantitative data from the post-test and pre-test suggest that videos are an effective input resource for teaching English. 85% of the participants demonstrate the learning of almost 95% of the English vocabulary, demonstrating that the collection of cooking videos as an Input Comprehensible used by the researcher had to some extent, advanced English language learning. On the other hand, the remaining percentage of learners who do not indicate English vocabulary learning is social and cognitive factors.

Analyzing the quantitative data obtained in the observation, educators are tired of working without technological material in large EFL classrooms. Scholars prefer to work with specialized resources that stimulate effective learning. This study reveals that audio-visual technology was perceived as effective for three reasons: it increases students' English vocabulary knowledge, is a medium for social and cognitive development, and allows educators to work on students' creativity and artistic aspects. Furthermore, it was evident that the collection of videos positively impacted the students and the entire YouTube community.

The need to work on students' motivation to learn EFL is ratified, creating activities that encourage creativity and instruments for more effective learning. On the other hand, educators should carry out projects that use audio-visual tools with compressible input to teach a language with daily life activities. Finally, it is recommended that the teaching-learning process of the vocabulary be done via a different activity that promotes creativity, such as arts and crafts, sports, and cooking.

In summary, this paper supports the idea that videos in the ELT classrooms play a fundamental role in helping students understand a foreign language. Besides, they can improve learners' performance by assessing specific vocabulary. In other words, cooking videos substantially influenced English comprehension and acquisition.

6. Conclusions

Based on the literature review and the results obtained in the empirical part of this study, the research team declares that the intended objectives have been fully achieved. Thus, 100% of the participants had a positive result in vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension of the recipes in the English language. The main contribution of this study is the innovation, the creative contribution to teaching the English language and how the preparation of cooking recipes safely has been highlighted, contributing to the acquisition of the English language vocabulary of the participants and increasing the motivation to learn. The weakness of this work is that the corpus of the sample, being limited, does not allow generalizations to be made; however, it already proposes work routes that can be implemented in teaching foreign languages to students at the secondary school level. Therefore, the scientific community is invited to continue executing new studies that contribute to innovation and creativity in teaching and learning English as a foreign language.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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